

LEARNING STRATEGIES FOR DEVELOPING SPEAKING ABILITY IN ENGLISH.

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Annotation: This article considers the effective methods of improving speaking skills of people. Additionally, there are some instructions which can help to individuals deal with the difficulties happening during making conservation.

Key words: filler words, improving speaking, reading, writing, listening, grammar, vocabulary, comprehension, fluency, pronunciation.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются эффективные методы улучшения разговорных навыков людей. Кроме того, есть некоторые инструкции, которые могут помочь людям справиться с трудностями, возникающими при консервации.

Ключевые слова: слова-заполнители, улучшение речи, чтения, письма, аудирования, грамматики, словарного запаса, понимания беглости, произношения.

In this age of globalization, English language is one of the key factors in terms of communication in all fields such as education, business, media in every part of world. That is why, the number of individuals who are learning English language as a second language is increasing at an alarming rate. Unfortunately, they come across with some problems especially in speaking. A person can achieve a communicative goal with the help of the fluency in speaking. Considering other skills in English like reading, writing as well as listening seems to be more vital for learners, but they should have the ability of speaking in order to perform conversation easily and effectively with other people. Why we need speaking? If we pay attention to this question in more detail, we will understand that it gives an opportunity to express our emotions which cannot be done through writing and it also helps us to exchange

our ideas orally. Thus, among four key language skills, speaking is seemed to be more important one which must be mastered well in learning a new language. However, mastering speaking ability is not easy task for learners. Learners think speaking as the most difficult skill, because it requires a lot of practice, courage as well as preparation to speak in foreign language. According to the idea of Brown, he says that there are five components in speaking, they are grammar, vocabulary, comprehension, fluency and pronunciation. Learners should be aware of these key factors. In addition, they should know what they are saying prior to speaking, therefore they ought to have some ideas in their minds about what they will say to others. Furthermore, speakers must know how to pronounce the words correctly, otherwise it can be difficult for listeners to understand the meaning of the sentences. Moreover, students must have sufficient vocabulary so as to be able to speak fluently and correctly. If all of these things are done very well, the students obviously speak well and listeners also get their information without any misunderstandings.

There are some problems for speaking skills that students confront with them while speaking among others. They are to make pauses, fear of making mistakes, lack of confidence, shyness, using a lot filler words and others. Here some tips for tackling these challenges.

1.Lack of confidence is one of the reasons why students cannot speak in public like among their mates or teachers. If they do not feel confident about their speaking in English to somehow, it is fault of teachers or experts in terms of English language, because they do not give enough encouragement to students about speaking in front of people. Students always learn English, but not how to speak. This is one of the problems that students face during speaking in classroom or in front of individuals. Self- confidence has positive impact on speaking English language, if students do not believe in themselves, they cannot speak very well. It is the responsibility of teachers to encourage students to believe in themselves. When students are worried from making mistakes, teachers should tell one motto them like no one can be born perfectly, everyone can learn from their mistakes. It can be motivation for students.

2. Shyness is another problem in speaking. It depends on characteristics of students, some of them are extrovert, while some of them are introvert. Students are unable to speak about what they are thinking in front of their friends or their teachers due to the shyness. In this case, they cannot remember grammar rules and correct vocabulary, even though they try to do that. Due to shyness, they feel uncomfortable and anxious among others during speaking. For tackling this problem, teachers should give motivational speeches and also force them to imitate these videos. By imitating every detail of these people in pronunciation, mimics as well as facial expressions, students can lose their shyness.

3. Fear of making mistakes in speaking is also one of the biggest problems for students. To be precise, they are worried by making grammatical or some mistakes in front of their mates, because they laugh at them or teachers look silly to them, even their classmates criticize them in the classroom. That is why some students try not speak. In this case teachers should create friendly atmosphere among students and try to make friendly relationship among them, additionally, teachers should teach children to continue without fear even if they make mistakes while speaking, they can help to lose the fear of making mistakes.

4. Using a lot of filler words is another problem. Students think that when they want to gather their ideas in their minds or to organize the structure of the sentences, they prefer using filler words like "errr, like, umm, you know" instead of making pauses. In order to deal with this problem, students should make some pauses during speaking or use silent sounds.

5. The greatest fear of a person with poor communication skills is the pause. The sound of silence between sentences makes them feel like they are under the gun of judgement. The truth is that using pauses correctly adds more value to our speech. All good speakers use pauses to best effect. If we need extra time to gather our words, pause, even if we're in between sentences. Sometimes we may pause at inconvenient points, but we know the difference between good and bad pauses. A

little silence works better than misuse of words. Also, pausing makes us look more thoughtful.

To sum up, students face some problems such as shyness, fear of making mistakes, using filler words and lack of confidence during speaking in English language. Teachers should give some above mentioned instructions, encouragement and help them to overcome their problems in order to speak very well in a foreign language.

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